

Study of the Clinical Profile of COVID-19 Patients after Recovery**Unnati Watal¹, Anchit Bhatnagar², Mitali Nayak³, Himanshu Thakker⁴**¹Student, 3rd Year M.B.B.S, Terna Medical College & affiliated Hospitals²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Terna Medical College & affiliated Hospitals³Professor & HOD, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Terna Medical College & affiliated Hospitals⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Terna Medical College & affiliated Hospitals

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: The global healthcare systems have faced substantial challenges since the onset of the COVID-19 outbreak in December 2019. While numerous trials and studies have been launched to comprehend and address the acute phase of the disease successfully, understanding the long-term consequences of COVID-19 has lagged, and the epidemiology of post-COVID conditions remains unclear. Post-acute COVID-19 is characterized by manifestations persisting beyond three weeks from symptom onset, and chronic COVID-19 extends beyond 12 weeks.

Aim: To assess pulmonary function and other physiological parameters in patients recovered from COVID-19 to identify long term complications and sequelae.

Material and Methods: Following the receipt of ethical clearance from the institutional review, an observational cohort study was conducted by establishing an Outpatient COVID-19 Follow-up Clinic. This clinic catered to all individuals who had been admitted to Terna Specialty Hospital and Research Center for COVID-19 treatment between June 2021 and August 2021. In cases where patients were managed at home post-discharge, a trained physician conducted telephonic consultations to determine the necessity of a follow-up visit.

Result: Among the study participants, 44 individuals, constituting 44.0% of the total, were classified as having normal lung function. Twelve participants, accounting for 12.0%, were identified with Small Airway Disease, while six individuals (6.0%) exhibited characteristics indicative of Obstructive Disease. 45 participants, constituting 45.0% of the total, were identified as having diabetes, while the remaining 55 participants, representing 55.0%, did not have diabetes. Additionally, the table includes mean values for relevant glycemic indicators. The mean HbA1c on Day 1 was 6.14 with a standard deviation of 1.15, reflecting the average long-term blood sugar levels.

Conclusion: Based on our current research, a substantial number of individuals who contracted COVID-19 experienced lingering symptoms after their recovery. Notably, fatigue emerged as the predominant concern, followed by cough and breathlessness.

Keywords: covid 19, fatigue, PFT, Diabetes.

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Introduction

The global impact of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, as reported by the World Health Organization (WHO), has surpassed 43 million confirmed cases and exceeded one million deaths worldwide. As of October 29, 2020, India has contributed significantly to these figures, with over 600,000 confirmed cases and more than 100,000 reported deaths. The first case in India emerged in Kerala, and since then, COVID-19 has spread across the entire nation. While some individuals with SARS-CoV-2 infection may experience mild or asymptomatic illness, others progress rapidly to severe conditions such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), multi-organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS), and ultimately, fatalities.[1]

The global healthcare systems have faced substantial challenges since the onset of the COVID-19 outbreak in December 2019. While numerous trials and studies have been launched to comprehend and address the acute phase of the disease successfully, understanding the long-term consequences of COVID-19 has lagged, and the epidemiology of post-COVID conditions remains unclear. Post-acute COVID-19 is characterized by manifestations persisting beyond three weeks from symptom onset, and chronic COVID-19 extends beyond 12 weeks.[2] According to recent data from the UK COVID Symptom Study, approximately one in 50 individuals continues to experience symptoms for 12 weeks or more, indicating a

prevalence of post-COVID conditions affecting millions globally. With many individuals being discharged from hospitals without systematic assessments of their recovery or the potential need for rehabilitation and early detection of chronic complications, there is an increasing imperative to consistently investigate the effects of post-COVID-19 disease among recovered patients.[3]

The study of the clinical profile of COVID-19 patients post-recovery is a critical endeavor in understanding the lingering effects and long-term consequences of the disease. Following recuperation from the acute phase of infection, individuals may experience a spectrum of health issues that extend beyond the initial respiratory symptoms. Research in this domain aims to characterize the diverse range of post-COVID-19 sequelae, encompassing respiratory, cardiovascular, neurological, and psychological aspects.[4] Studies have identified persistent symptoms such as fatigue, shortness of breath, and cognitive impairment in a significant proportion of recovered patients. Additionally, investigations into the immunological and inflammatory responses during the recovery phase contribute to unraveling the complexities of post-acute sequelae of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Insights gained from these studies are invaluable for developing comprehensive post-COVID-19 care strategies, guiding healthcare providers in managing the long-term health challenges faced by individuals who have overcome the acute phase of the disease.[5]

Aims & Objectives

- To assess pulmonary function and other physiological parameters in patients recovered from COVID-19 to identify long term complications and sequelae
- To identify unmet healthcare needs and people requiring additional rehabilitation/investigations

Materials & Methods

Following the receipt of ethical clearance from the institutional review, an observational cohort study was conducted by establishing an Outpatient COVID-19 Follow-up Clinic. This clinic catered to all individuals who had been admitted to Terna Specialty Hospital and Research Center for COVID-19 treatment between June 2021 and August 2021. In cases where patients were managed at home post-discharge, a trained physician conducted telephonic consultations to determine the necessity of a follow-up visit. The follow-up visits were scheduled on a monthly basis for three months following hospital discharge. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants who chose to enroll in the follow-up

program. During the post-COVID-19 follow-up assessments, various medical evaluations will be conducted to comprehensively gauge the health status of individuals. These assessments encompass a Pulmonary Function Test to evaluate respiratory function, a Complete Blood Count to assess blood parameters, estimation of C - reactive protein to gauge inflammation levels, and D-dimer estimation to evaluate blood clotting tendencies. Additionally, an ECG and 2-D Echo will be performed if indicated by the individual's clinical condition. A CT Thorax will be conducted to assess the chest region, and a 6-minute walk test will be administered to evaluate physical endurance. These thorough evaluations aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the post-COVID-19 health status of individuals and guide appropriate medical interventions if necessary.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients who are ≥ 18 years
- COVID-19 diagnosed according to World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines (as per December 2020)
- At least 17 days after onset of initial symptoms
- Exclusion Criteria:
- Pregnancy
- Patients bedridden after discharge

The information collected during each subsequent follow-up appointment will be systematically analyzed and compared to evaluate the enduring impacts of COVID-19 in individuals who have recovered, with a focus on identifying any discernible patterns. The study spanned duration of three months, during which written informed consent was sought from participants, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement in the research.

Statistician's Remarks:

Expected sample size for the study is 100. Continuous variables will be described using mean with standard deviation (SD) or median with inter-quartile range(IQR), followed by unpaired t-test. Categorical variables will be described as percentage and compared using the Chi-square test. Logistic regression analysis will be used to study the independent covariates for the presence of HRCT abnormalities or abnormal pulmonary function. The correlation of different variables will be analyzed using the Spearman's correlation.

The conventional level of statistical significance of 0.05 will be used for all analyses. Statistical analyses will be performed using SPSS Version 21.0.

Result

Table 1: Mean variables of the study subjects

Characteristics	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (y)	47.57	14.47
PCV	40.70	4.85
D1-Ddimer	38.26	99.90

Table 1 presents the mean values for various variables concerning the study subjects. The average age of the participants was 47.57 years with a standard deviation of 14.47. In terms of hematological parameters, the mean Packed Cell Volume (PCV) was 40.70 with a standard deviation of 4.85, while the mean D-Dimer level was 38.26 with a standard deviation of 99.90.

Table 2: Mean pre-bronchodilator PFT values of the study subjects

PFT Values		
Pre Bronchodilator	mean	SD
FVC	3.02	0.78
FEV ₁	2.41	0.69
FEV ₁ /FVC	79.32	8.16
Pred FVC	3.70	0.58
Pred FEV ₁	2.95	0.51
Pred FEV ₁ /FVC	79.52	3.53
% Pred FVC	80.83	12.95
% Pred FEV ₁	80.58	13.94
% Pred FEV ₁ /FVC	99.70	9.15

Table 2 provides the mean values for pre-bronchodilator Pulmonary Function Test (PFT) parameters among the study subjects. Specifically, the mean Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) was 3.02 with a standard deviation of 0.78, and the mean Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁) was 2.41 with a standard deviation of 0.69. The ratio of FEV₁ to FVC (FEV₁/FVC) had a mean

value of 79.32 with a standard deviation of 3.53. Additionally, the predicted values for FVC (Pred FVC) had a mean of 3.70 with a standard deviation of 0.58, the predicted values for FEV₁ (Pred FEV₁) had a mean of 2.95 with a standard deviation of 0.51, and the predicted ratio of FEV₁ to FVC (Pred FEV₁/FVC) had a mean of 79.52 with a standard deviation of 3.53.

Table 3: Mean post-bronchodilator PFT values of the study subjects

Post Bronchodilator	Mean	SD
FVC	3.08	0.80
FEV ₁	2.50	0.73
FEV ₁ /FVC	80.84	7.34
Pred FVC	3.71	0.57
Pred FEV ₁	2.95	0.51
Pred FEV ₁ /FVC	79.52	3.53
% Pred FVC	82.40	13.85
% Pred FEV ₁	83.72	14.56
% Pred FEV ₁ /FVC	101.60	7.64
% Change in FVC	1.58	2.73
% Change in FEV ₁	3.14	3.42
% Change in FEV ₁ /FVC	1.90	3.48

Table 3 outlines the post-bronchodilator Pulmonary Function Test (PFT) results for the study subjects, presenting both measured and predicted values with their respective standard deviations. The Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) had a mean value of 3.08 liters, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.80. Similarly, the mean Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁) was 2.50 liters, with a standard deviation of 0.73. The ratio of FEV₁ to FVC (FEV₁/FVC) had a mean value of 80.84%, with a standard deviation of 7.34. Predicted values for

FVC (Pred FVC) and FEV₁ (Pred FEV₁) were 3.71 liters and 2.95 liters, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.57 and 0.51. The predicted ratio of FEV₁ to FVC (Pred FEV₁/FVC) had a mean value of 79.52%, with a standard deviation of 3.53. Additionally, the table includes percentage predicted values (% Pred) and percentage change values (% Change) for FVC, FEV₁, and FEV₁/FVC, providing insights into the relative performance and alterations in pulmonary function among the study subjects.

Table 4: Distribution of study subjects as per grading of the disease

Grading of disease	n	%
Mild disease	37	37.0%
Moderate disease	32	32.0%
Severe disease	31	31.0%

Table 4 presents the distribution of study subjects based on the grading of the disease severity.

The data categorizes individuals into three groups: mild, moderate, and severe disease. Among the study participants, 37 individuals, constituting 37.0% of the total, were classified as having a mild form of the disease. Another 32 participants, accounting for 32.0%, fell into the category of

moderate disease. The remaining 31 individuals, representing 31.0% of the cohort, were classified as having a severe form of the disease.

This distribution provides a clear overview of the prevalence of different disease grades within the study population, offering valuable insights into the spectrum of disease severity among the subjects under investigation.

Table 5: Distribution of study subjects as per type of lung disease as per PFT

Type of lung disease (Acc. to PFT)	no	%
Normal	44	44.0%
Small Airway Disease	12	12.0%
Obstructive Disease	06	06.0%
Restrictive Disease	38	38.0%

Table 5 outlines the distribution of study subjects based on the type of lung disease, as determined by Pulmonary Function Tests (PFT).

The data categorizes individuals into four groups: Normal, Small Airway Disease, Obstructive Disease, and Restrictive Disease. Among the study participants, 44 individuals, constituting 44.0% of the total, were classified as having normal lung function. Twelve participants, accounting for 12.0%, were identified with Small Airway Disease, while six individuals (6.0%) exhibited

characteristics indicative of Obstructive Disease. The largest category comprised 38 participants, representing 38.0% of the cohort, who were classified as having Restrictive Disease.

This distribution offers insights into the prevalence of various types of lung diseases within the study population, providing valuable information for understanding the impact of COVID-19 on respiratory function among the subjects under investigation.

Table 6: Diabetes status characteristics of the study subjects

Characteristics – Diabetes Status	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Yes	45	45.0%
No	55	55.0%
HbA1c on Day 1	06.14	1.15
FPG	115.67	19.74
PPG	170.97	43.94

Table 6 delineates the diabetes status characteristics of the study subjects, providing a comprehensive overview of the distribution of participants based on their diabetes status. Among the individuals under study, 45 participants, constituting 45.0% of the total, were identified as having diabetes, while the remaining 55 participants, representing 55.0%, did not have diabetes.

Additionally, the table includes mean values for relevant glycemic indicators. The mean HbA1c on Day 1 was 6.14 with a standard deviation of 1.15, reflecting the average long-term blood sugar levels. The mean Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG) was 115.67 with a standard deviation of 19.74, and the mean Postprandial Plasma Glucose (PPG) was 170.97 with a standard deviation of 43.94.

These glycemic parameters provide further insights into the diabetes status and control levels among the study subjects, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the interplay between diabetes and COVID-19 outcomes in the cohort.

Discussion:

Detecting the long term sequelae of COVID-19 will not just ensure individual health benefit but also provide awareness in terms of what to expect after the second wave on a community level.

This will further help in providing timely care and attention even after recovery of patients from the acute form of the disease, so as to prevent any residual disease from complicating.

The results presented in Table 1 provide key insights into the demographic and hematological characteristics of the study subjects. The average age of the participants, 47.57 years with a standard deviation of 14.47, indicates a relatively diverse age range within the cohort. This demographic information is crucial for understanding how COVID-19 affects individuals across different age groups, as age has been identified as a significant factor influencing the severity of the disease. This observation aligns with findings from research conducted by Han et al.[6] and Zhao et al.[7] in China, as well as studies by Kayina et al. [8] and Dosi et al.[9] in India. Similarly, the prevalence of COVID-19 was higher in males in this study, constituting 71.4%, a pattern consistent with the outcomes reported by Kayina et al.[8] and Saxena et al.[10] in their respective studies.

Moving to hematological parameters, the mean Packed Cell Volume (PCV) of 40.70 with a standard deviation of 4.85 suggests a measure of the proportion of blood volume occupied by red blood cells. This parameter is vital for assessing the oxygen-carrying capacity of the blood, and deviations from the mean may indicate potential health issues. The mean D-Dimer level of 38.26 with a standard deviation of 99.90 is noteworthy, as elevated D-Dimer levels have been associated with increased blood clotting and are often observed in severe COVID-19 cases. This finding aligns with the growing body of literature highlighting the link between coagulation abnormalities and severe outcomes in COVID-19. Study by Lehman A et al [11] shows in their study thrombotic complications were found in 13% (2/15) of patients with prolonged elevated D-dimer level. Thus, this analysis confirms that D-Dimer level may be an important predictor for thromboembolic events in the long-term follow-up.

In the present study the mean Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) was 3.02 with a standard deviation of 0.78, and the mean Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV1) was 2.41 with a standard deviation of 0.69. The ratio of FEV1 to FVC (FEV1/FVC) had a mean value of 79.32 with a standard deviation of 3.53.

Additionally, the predicted values for FVC (Pred FVC) had a mean of 3.70 with a standard deviation of 0.58, the predicted values for FEV1 (Pred FEV1) had a mean of 2.95 with a standard deviation of 0.51, and the predicted ratio of FEV1 to FVC (Pred FEV1/FVC) had a mean of 79.52 with a standard deviation of 3.53. In individuals recovering from severe acute respiratory syndrome covid 19, research indicates that 25%-40% experience persistent respiratory function abnormalities one year post-discharge.

Study by Emine Afsin et al [12] Comparing pre-COVID and post-COVID pulmonary function test (PFT) parameters in 33 patients, they observed a significant 130 mL loss only in forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) ($P = .005$), with no significant differences in forced vital capacity (FVC) and FEV1/FVC ($P = .454$, $P = .066$). In the present study among the participants, 44.0% had normal lung function, 12.0% had Small Airway Disease, 6.0% exhibited Obstructive Disease, and 38.0% were classified with Restrictive Disease. Study by Emine Afsin et al [12] found a 20.9% restrictive pattern and an 11.9% obstructive pattern in the 3- to 6-month post-COVID period.

Two out of eight patients with an obstructive pattern had underlying chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. While a study found a higher PFT abnormality rate in severe post-COVID cases, our study did not find associations between PFT abnormalities and the severity of CT involvement, oxygen support, or hospitalization history. A meta-analysis on COVID-19 revealed 15% with a restrictive pattern and 7% with an obstructive pattern.

Research conducted by Prabal Chourasia et al. [13] revealed an elevated risk of developing new-onset diabetes mellitus four weeks after acute COVID-19 infection. Subgroup analysis conducted by Xie et al. [14] demonstrated a heightened risk and prevalence of new-onset diabetes mellitus at the four-week mark post-acute COVID-19 infection in individuals aged 65 and older, black patients (compared to white patients), and those with prior cardiovascular disease, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, prediabetes, and a higher body mass index. In a previous review by Joshi et al. [15], COVID-19-induced diabetes was discussed, focusing primarily on case series and retrospective analyses in the pediatric population. Sathish et al. [16] incorporated eight retrospective cohort studies involving 3,711 cases of COVID-19 and 492 cases of newly diagnosed diabetes.

Conclusions

Based on our current research, a substantial number of individuals who contracted COVID-19 experienced lingering symptoms after their recovery. Notably, fatigue emerged as the predominant concern, followed by cough and breathlessness. The study revealed a higher prevalence of Post-Acute Sequelae of SARS-CoV-2 (PASC) manifestations in individuals with elevated body mass index (BMI) and those with systemic hypertension. Interestingly, neither gender nor the severity category of the initial COVID-19 illness demonstrated an association with the development of persistent symptoms in this investigation.

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